

INFLUENCE OF STUDENT MISBEHAVIOUR AND STRESS ON JOB WITHDRAWAL BEHAVIOUR AMONG COLLEGE TEACHERS

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Abstract

Workplace stress, student misbehavior and poor performance increase teachers' job dissatisfaction and induce job withdrawal behavior. The data was collected from 50 Arts and Science College Teachers in Cuddalore district. The analysis discovered that there is direct effect of student misbehaviour and stress on job dissatisfaction and job withdrawal behaviour. The research also identified that there is indirect effect of student misbehaviour and stress on job withdrawal behaviour. Finally, the research discovered that there is direct effect of job dissatisfaction on job withdrawal behaviour. Hence, it is recommended that college management should provide the necessary support and healthy working environment to the teachers to control their work pressure. Also, appropriate support should be provided to handle the students through proper training and development programs.

Keywords: Student Misbehavior, Stress, Job Dissatisfaction and Job Withdrawal Behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

Student misbehavior and work pressures have recently become a major problem in educational institutions. Also, increased job responsibilities and longer working hours in the workplace are becoming progressively more stressful for teachers. Both the faculty and the college understand job stress as a physical and psychological concept. Job stress affects teachers' health problems. Workplace stress, student misbehavior and poor performance increase teachers' job dissatisfaction and induce job withdrawal behavior. Student misbehavior and work pressure creates a negative reaction among teachers. As a result, in a highly competitive workplace environment where job stress increases, teachers gradually change their behavior and adopt job dissatisfaction and withdrawal behavior. Hence, the research tries to identify the influence of student misbehaviour and stress on job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ibrahim A. Elshaer, Alaa M. S. Azazz and Sameh Fayyad (2022) found that work withdrawal behavior was influenced by hotel employee stress. The research also identified the capability of task-coping reduced hotel employee work withdrawal behavior.

Mohamed Dawood Shamout, Malek Bakheet Haroun Elayan, Salima Hamouche, Adnan M. Rawashdeh and Hamzah Elrehail (2022) discovered the work withdrawal positively influenced by Techno stress at various educational sectors in Saudi Arabia. But no significant gender variations occurred.

Ode Ewonshega Joseph and Asakpa O. Romeo (2021) discovered that overcrowded classes, lack of resources, administrative issues, lack of discipline and lack of recognition by Principals caused dissatisfaction among teachers. The research also identified that job dissatisfaction had caused disengagement in some teachers and lack of focus in their profession.

Tomislava Vidic, Marina Duranovi and Irena Klasnic (2021) identified that the student misbehaviour and satisfaction with help from parents extensively contribute to satisfaction. The research also identified that emotional exhaustion, teaching profession and depersonalization lead to decrease of teachers' job satisfaction.

Ni Made Umayanti Prateka Atmaja and I Gusti Salit Ketut Netra (2020) identified that job stress and work-family conflict had a significant and positive effect on physical withdrawal behavior. The research also identified that job satisfaction had a significant and negative effect on employee physical withdrawal behavior.

Navaneethkrishnan Kengatharan (2020) found that student behavior and teacher autonomy positively correlate to teacher job satisfaction. The research also identified that there is influence of student behavior on teacher job satisfaction with respect to student engagement.

Joshua Pittman (2020) found that behaviors for the workplace and person's emotions may influence their job satisfaction. The research also identified that there is a significant relationship between student discipline and teacher job satisfaction.

Aziz Rhnima and Claudio Pousa (2017) discovered that influence of family interferences with work such as time and behavior on withdrawal behaviors. The research also identified that stress management (work interferences with family) such as time, strain and behavior influence on withdrawal behaviors.

James Manalel and Manu Melwin Joy (2016) discovered that employee withdrawal behavior was negatively influenced by job satisfaction among employees working in IT industry.

Elhameh HajiGhasemi and Elhameh HajiGhasemi (2013) identified that present of counter-productive behavior changes was negatively explained job satisfaction such as extrinsic satisfaction and inner satisfaction. The result showed that job satisfaction such as extrinsic satisfaction and inner satisfaction negatively influence present of withdrawal behavior changes.

Jessie Lynn Johnson (2003) found that negative relationship between student misbehavior and teachers' job satisfaction. The research also identified that negative relationship between principal and coworker support and teachers' job satisfaction. The results show that both types of discipline (student misbehavior and principal & coworker support) negatively affect teachers' job satisfaction.

Teacher stress in the classroom has been associated consistently with students' negative behavior (Blase, 1986; Geving, 2007; Borg and Riding, 1991; Brouwers & Tomic, 2000; Evers, et al. 2004; Gable, et al. 2009; Hastings & Bham, 2003). Among the above studies, there are numerous studies on how student behaviors affect teacher stress. Also, there is not much research on how teacher stress affects student behavior in the classroom (Geving, 2007).

Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Limited research has been conducted related to student misbehavior, stress, job dissatisfaction and job withdrawal behaviour. Hence, the study attempts to fill this gap by estimating the impact of student misbehavior and stress on job dissatisfaction and job withdrawal behavior among college teachers. Below are my proposed hypotheses.

- H1:** Student misbehavior has significantly influences job dissatisfaction among college teachers.
- H2:** Stress has significantly influences job dissatisfaction among college teachers.
- H3:** Student misbehavior has significantly influences job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers.
- H4:** Stress has significantly influences job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers.
- H5:** Job dissatisfaction has significantly influences job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers.

Need For the Study

The findings of this study will help college management. This study will help to know whether the college teachers are satisfied who have received job satisfaction in their institution. This study also will help to identify the factors influencing job withdrawal behaviours. Findings from this study can help college management increase job satisfaction and decrease job withdrawal behaviours.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers' job withdrawal behaviors adversely affect the educational institutions (colleges). Internationally, workforce withdrawal behaviors consume around 15% of business organization's payroll (Faulk & Hicks, 2015). Job withdrawal behaviour and job dissatisfaction are business related constructs that have been extensively researched and directly influenced by student misbehavior and stress. A common problem in the educational institution is that faculty withdrawal behavior affects the effectiveness of an educational institution. A particular problem for the educational institution is that some educational institution leaders do not have the necessary procedures in place to prevent the effects of teacher withdrawal behaviors due to work stress and student misbehavior.

OBJECTIVES

- To discover the influence of student misbehavior and stress on job dissatisfaction among college teachers.
- To find out the influence of job dissatisfaction on job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to explore the influence of student misbehaviour and stress on job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers a descriptive research design is employed by the researcher. Data is collected from college teachers in Cuddalore district, Tamilnadu through a well-designed questionnaire. This descriptive research design is employed to explore the relationship between student misbehavior, stress, job dissatisfaction and job withdrawal behaviour.

Questionnaire Design

Data is collected from college teachers in Cuddalore district, Tamilnadu through a well-designed questionnaire. The questionnaire construction for this study is divided into five parts. The first part of the questionnaire is a demographic profile of the college teachers, the second part is student misbehavior, the third part is stress, the fourth part is job dissatisfaction and the fifth part is job withdrawal behaviour. The first part is set up as a category and the other three as a measuring scaling technique.

Table 1: Questionnaire Construction

S. No.	Variable	Items	Author
1	Demographic Profile	10	---
2	Student Misbehavior	4	Michael S. Sturmfels (2009)
3	Stress	9	
4	Job Dissatisfaction	15	Shamim Talukder, et al. (2014)
5	Job Withdrawal Behaviour	25	Erdemli (2015)

Reliability

Pilot study was done to confirm that the results of this research questionnaire are reliable. The questionnaires are verified by involving 50 Arts and Science College teachers. Based on the Arts and Science College teachers' opinion, some changes are made in the questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha tool is employed to test the reliability. All the variables of this questionnaire are above 0.70. The results show that it is reliable. This means that the questionnaire has a high reliability value.

Table 2: Reliability of the research

S. No.	Variable	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Student Misbehavior	4	0.87
2	Stress	9	0.90
3	Job Dissatisfaction	15	0.94
4	Job Withdrawal Behaviour	25	0.83

Source: Primary data

Sampling Technique

In this study, purposive sampling technique has been applied to collect the primary data from Arts and Science College teachers in Cuddalore district. In this way 50 Arts and Science College teachers are approached to collect the primary data.

Statistical Tools

Path analysis is used to estimate model by probing the relationship between independent variables (student misbehavior and stress) on dependent variable (job dissatisfaction and job withdrawal behaviours). The researcher has employed the path analysis for influence of student misbehavior and stress on job withdrawal behaviours with respect to job dissatisfaction.

Figure 1.2: Influence of student misbehaviour and stress on job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers

Table 3: Model Fit Indication

S. No.	Model Fit Indicators	Calculated Values in the Analysis	Recommended Values (Premapriya, et al. 2016)
1	Chi-Square	4.107	---
2	p	0.072	> 0.050
3	GFI	0.988	> 0.90
4	AGFI	0.939	
5	CFI	0.988	
6	NFI	0.985	
7	RMR	0.044	< 0.080
8	RMSEA	0.036	

Source: Primary data

The table 3 presents the mode summary of influence of student misbehaviour and stress on job withdrawal behaviour among college teachers. The path model presented, along with mode summary to verify the model fitness. The Chi-square statistic is 4.107 with $p > 0.05$. The table illustrates the model fit statistics such as RMSEA, RMR, NFI, CFI, AGFI and GFI. RMR and RMSEA are within than the recommended limit i.e., RMR and RMSEA is less than 0.08 (Indra, Balaji and Velaudham, 2020; Velaudham and Baskar, 2016). NFI, CFI, AGFI and GFI are within than the recommended limit i.e., NFI, CFI, AGFI and GFI is greater than 0.90 (Kantiah Alias Deepak and Velaudham, 2019; Velaudham and Baskar, 2015). All the model fit statistics imply a better model fit (Premapriya, et al. 2016; Victor and Velaudham, 2020).

Table 4: Regression Weights

DV		IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	p
Job Dissatisfaction	<---	Student Misbehaviour	0.210	0.030	6.953	0.318	0.001
Job Dissatisfaction	<---	Stress	0.212	0.032	6.704	0.307	0.001
Job Withdrawal Behaviours	<---	Job Dissatisfaction	0.358	0.033	10.736	0.347	0.001
Job Withdrawal Behaviours	<---	Student Misbehaviour	0.202	0.023	8.740	0.296	0.001
Job Withdrawal Behaviours	<---	Stress	0.244	0.024	10.129	0.342	0.001

Source: Primary data

H₁: Student misbehaviour significantly influences job dissatisfaction among college teachers.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrated that the C.R. value is 6.953; β value is 0.318 and p value is significant. The value of β is 0.318 that student misbehaviour explains 31.8 percent of the job dissatisfaction. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrated that the student misbehaviour significantly influence job dissatisfaction among college teachers. Jessie Lynn Johnson (2003) found that negative relationship between student misbehavior and teachers' job satisfaction.

H₂: Stress significantly influences job dissatisfaction among college teachers.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrated that the C.R. value is 6.704; β value is 0.307 and p value is significant. The value of β is 0.307 that stress explains 30.7 percent of the job dissatisfaction. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrated that the stress significantly influence job dissatisfaction among college teachers. Ni Made Umayanti Prateka Atmaja and I GustiSalitKetut Netra (2020) identified that job stress and work-family conflict had a significant and positive effect on physical withdrawal behavior.

H₃: Student misbehaviour significantly influences job withdrawal behaviours among college teachers.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrated that the C.R. value is 8.740; β value is 0.296 and p value is significant. The value of β is 0.296 that student misbehaviour explains 29.6 percent of the job withdrawal behaviours. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrated that the student misbehaviour significantly influence job withdrawal behaviours among college teachers.

H4: Stress significantly influences job withdrawal behaviours among college teachers.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrated that the C.R. value is 10.129; β value is 0.342 and p value is significant. The value of β is 0.342 that stress explains 34.2 percent of the job withdrawal behaviours. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrated that the stress significantly influence job withdrawal behaviours among college teachers. Mohamed Dawood Shamout, et al. (2022) discovered the work withdrawal positively influenced by Techno stress

H5: Job dissatisfaction significantly influences job withdrawal behaviours among college teachers.

The hypothesis was tested in path model. The finding of the analysis demonstrated that the C.R. value is 10.736; β value is 0.347 and p value is significant. The value of β is 0.347 that job dissatisfaction explains 34.7 percent of the job withdrawal behaviours. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrated that the job dissatisfaction significantly influence job withdrawal behaviours among college teachers. Ni Made Umayanti Prateka Atmaja and I GustiSalitKetut Netra (2020) identified that job satisfaction had a significant and negative effect on employee physical withdrawal behavior.

FINDINGS

The analysis discovered that there is direct effect of j student misbehaviour and stress on job dissatisfaction and job withdrawal behaviour. Jessie Lynn Johnson (2003) found that negative relationship between student misbehavior and teachers' job satisfaction. Ni Made Umayanti Prateka Atmaja and I GustiSalitKetut Netra (2020) identified that job stress and work-family conflict had a significant and positive effect on physical withdrawal behavior. The research also identified that there is indirect effect of student misbehaviour and stress on job withdrawal behaviour. Finally, the research discovered that there is direct effect of job dissatisfaction on job withdrawal behaviour. Ni Made Umayanti Prateka Atmaja and I GustiSalitKetut Netra (2020) identified that job satisfaction had a significant and negative effect on employee physical withdrawal behavior.

RECOMMENDATION

College managements should develop incentive packages to increase the motivation of teachers to improve job satisfaction. Also, special attention should be given to increasing wages. At the time of data collection, majority of the teachers said that the salary was insufficient to meet their needs. Increasing teachers' salaries can increase their morale in teaching. It is necessary for the college management to provide the necessary support and healthy working environment to the teachers to control their work pressure. Also, appropriate support should be provided to handle the students through proper training and development programs.

CONCLUSION

The analysis discovered that there is direct effect of student misbehaviour and stress on job dissatisfaction and job withdrawal behaviour. The research also identified that there is indirect effect of student misbehaviour and stress on job withdrawal behaviour. Finally, the research discovered that there is direct effect of job dissatisfaction on job withdrawal behaviour. Hence, it is concluded that college management should provide the necessary support and healthy working environment to the teachers to control their work pressure. Also, appropriate support should be provided to handle the students through proper training and development programs.

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